

Resistance of Indonesian mutant lines to the brown planthopper (BPH) *Nilaparvata lugens*

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We tested seven mutant rice lines, derived from BPH-susceptible Pelita I/1, for resistance to BPH at IRRI. The lines came from the National Atomic Energy Agency in Jakarta, Indonesia. They were Atomita 1, 627/10-3/PsJ, Atomita 2, and 627/4-E/PsJ, derived from Pelita I/1 irradiated with 0.2 k Gy of gamma rays; and A227/2/PsJ, A227/3/PsJ, and A227/5/PsJ derived from an early-maturing mutant of Pelita I/1 irradiated with 0.1 k Gy of gamma rays. We conducted two tests with five replications to measure their level of resistance to BPH: seedbox screening for plant damage, and population growth.

In the seedbox screening test, seeds of entries were planted in seedboxes. Seven days after sowing, they were infested with eight second- and third-instar BPH nymphs/

Resistance of Indonesian mutant lines to BPH. IRRI, 1984.

seedling. Plant damage was rated when the susceptible check died.

In the second test, 30-d-old test plant were infested with 5 pair (male and female) of 2- to 3-d-old adult BPH and enclosed with mylar film cages. When their progeny reached adulthood on susceptible TN1 plants, the insects in all the cages were counted.

The Indonesian mutant lines were resistant to moderately resistant to biotype 1 and biotype 3, but susceptible to biotype 2 (see figure). Similar seedbox screening tests showed the mutant lines were moderately resistant to green leafhopper and whitebacked planthopper, as compared with susceptible TN1.

Atomita 2 has been released for commercial cultivation in Indonesia. In addition to its resistance to BPH biotype 1 and biotype 3, it has high yield potential, good eating quality, and salinity tolerance. □

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Varietal resistance of rice to whitebacked planthopper (WBPH)

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We evaluated 22 rice accessions from 7 countries for resistance to WBPH

Sogatella furcifera at the Paddy Breeding Station, Coimbatore. Using the seedling screening technique in the glasshouse, 86 accessions had a damage rating of 3 (Table 1). The resistant accessions were reevaluated in three replications.

Seven promising accessions — ARC10550, ARC6650, T7, IET5741,

ET6315, IET6123, and ET6311 — were further evaluated using alternate row testing and seedling screening in pots. In all tests, their damage rating was lower than 4, confirming their resistance to WBPH (Table 2). All seven were indicas from India.

Table 1. Source of rice accessions and their reaction to WBPH, Coimbatore, India.

Source	Accessions screened (no.)	Accessions (no.) at each damage rating ^a				
		1	3	5	7	9
India	181	3	60	52	28	38
Indonesia	1	0	1	0	0	0
Nepal	2	0	2	0	0	0
Pakistan	5	0	3	1	0	1
Philippines	24	5	7	9	3	0
Sri Lanka	8	1	4	1	1	1
Taiwan	1	0	0	0	0	1
Total	222	9	77	63	32	41

^aBy the 1980 Standard Evaluation System for Rice scale.

Table 2. WBPH resistance in 7 rice accessions, Coimbatore, India.^a

Accession	Damage rating (1-9 scale)		
	Seedling screening ^b technique	Seedling screening ^c in pots	Alternate row test ^d
ARC10550	1.67 a	1.67 a	1.80 a
ARC6650	2.33 ab	2.67 b	2.60 ab
T7	3.00 ab	3.33 b	3.00 b
IET5741	3.00 ab	3.33 b	3.40 b
IET6315	3.00 ab	3.00 b	3.40 b
IET6123	3.00 ab	3.67 b	3.00 b
IET6311	3.67 b	3.67 b	3.40 b
TN1 (susceptible check)	9.00 c	9.00 c	9.00 c

^aIn a column, means with a common letter do not differ significantly (P = 0.05). ^bMean of 3 replications. ^cMean of 6 replications. ^dMean of 5 replications.